

ORGANIZATION OF TECHNICAL CIRCLES

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Abstract In the article, the importance of practical education and its role in the education of deaf and hard-of-hearing children, the organization of the work of technical circles, the elimination of speech defects through mass forms of extracurricular activities and activities outside the classroom and special boarding schools, and correction information is provided.

Key words: disability, hard of hearing, deaf, speech impairment, correction, work, subject practical education, construction, construction, making, elements, technical club, extracurricular activities and special boarding school.

In the work experience of special boarding schools, there are various circles. From the point of view of connection with educational subjects, circles can be divided into three groups: subject-related, inter-subject and extra-subject circles.

Circles directly related to labor education are called subject-related circles. According to their content, these circles are a continuation of the work done by the students in the labor class, but the activity of the students becomes more complex and wider. Subject circles should never simply repeat what students have done before.

The most important among inter-subject circles are physical and technical circles. The content of students' activities in these circles comes from the name of the circle itself. In physical and technical circles, students' work facilities are usually of different models. In this case, students will be able to clarify certain laws studied in the physics course with examples. This helps in mastering the basics of science. This is on the one hand. On the other hand, students' model

construction, physical-technical circles are led by physics and technology teachers at the same time.

Extracurricular clubs are now more common in extracurricular activities. According to the content of students' activities, these circles can be different. In this case, we are talking about extracurricular clubs, which use special boarding school workshops as a material base for their work. Student activities rely on knowledge and skills acquired in technology classes.

For example, in one of the special boarding schools, the teacher offers the students to develop the design of the machine designed for cover work in order to increase labor productivity. Students will like this idea. They also develop several designs of such a machine and offer the best. During practical testing, this construction will be improved more and more. All this happens in the process of covering works.

Employees of the base enterprise and parents are often invited to lead extracurricular clubs. The teacher gives them methodical support.

The content of the work of the circles is determined in the programs. These programs are developed by methodical offices under the department of public education, as well as stations of young technicians and naturalists. Programs are designed for one and two academic years.

As an example, we will give one of the programs of the technical club on the subject of locksmith work, intended for students of the 5th-7th grade.

Preparation of products with details cut with a saw, smooth surfaces and details. Summarizing the knowledge gained in labor education classes and improving skills: basic information about cutting metal with a saw; safety rules to be observed when cutting metal with a saw: methods of cutting metal with a saw; the essence of the grinding process and the tools used in it, safety rules to be observed during grinding, grinding of saw surfaces.

Circuit training is usually held once a week for two hours. However, among students there are those who are not satisfied with this. It is possible to conduct more training with them, but for this, it is necessary to agree with the head of the class, because he knows well how each student learns other subjects.

There should not be more than 15 students in one circle, otherwise it will be difficult to guide each of them individually.

The work experience of advanced special boarding schools shows that the structure of the club training based on the special boarding school workshops is close to the combined (mixed) lesson structure. The reason for this is that a number of didactic issues are usually resolved in any group training. Pupils consider the preparation of a specific object of work to be the main goal of the club training.

The methods of teaching in circle classes are chosen based on the set didactic goals, the content of the educational material, and the level of preparation of the students and the teacher.

There are no special methods for circle training. Simple methods of labor education are used in them. However, the use of these methods has its own characteristics. For example, according to observations, the explanatory method is most often used among oral methods, and the narrative method is used the least. At first glance, this may seem like a mistake. It is known that students' cognitive activity increases when compared to other oral methods during conversation. But this is the peculiarity of using educational methods in circle classes. It turned out that the students, especially in the first lessons, did not like the interviews, because the interviews reminded them of the question-and-answer in regular classes.

The demonstration methods are characterized by the fact that students of V-VI classes are often shown instruction manuals, and graphic images are shown to

students of VIII-IX classes. This approach to work takes into account the graphic readiness of students.

Instruction occupies an important place among the methods of training in circle classes. Current and final instructions include: frontal, link and individual instructions; verbal, written, graphic instructions can be used. In other words, all types of instruction typical for labor education can be found in circle training. The methodology of conducting the instruction was considered earlier.

Various forms of organization of students' work (frontal, link, individual, with division of labor) are used in circle classes.

The choice of the form of organization of students' work largely depends on the objects of work that attract special attention in the class. The reason for this is that in the process of working outside the classroom, the following two cases must be taken into account at the same time:

- 1) teamwork has the greatest educational potential.
- 2) students strive to complete individual tasks that satisfy their interests and allow them to show their independence to the fullest.

Mass forms of extracurricular activities

All these forms of extracurricular activities allow to attract many students. Experience has confirmed that mass forms of extracurricular work are highly effective. They allow students to expand their imagination about the basics of modern production, introduce them to various professions. But, unfortunately, they cannot attract students to useful work, direct creative activity. Therefore, it is appropriate if students, for example, take part in thematic evenings, other forms of work outside the classroom, and also participate in some other club work. In some cases, it happens by itself. For example, the members of the club organize exhibitions where they present their work.

Many special boarding schools pay attention to the exhibition. Exhibitions are permanent and temporary. But it is better that exhibitions are permanent. In such exhibitions, the products made by students will be worn for years. In some special boarding schools, it has become a tradition for each student to leave a memento about himself. Such memory can be related not only to technical work, but also to agriculture, economy and household service. The exhibition is an important incentive for club members, an effective means of promoting participation in extracurricular activities. Often, good exhibitions are the pride of the entire special boarding school, a group of tour guides is organized under the exhibition, they provide services to guests, work with students of lower classes. At the exhibitions, each club submits its work results to public judgment.

Great importance is attached to the political-educational, cultural-public and sports work of students in production brigades. Self-management of students provides a great opportunity for this. The general meeting of the students' brigade resolves the following most important issues: discusses the educational and production plan of the work and determines the ways of its implementation. Confirms the terms of the competition; considers issues related to the discipline and life of the brigade members and resolves the issue of incentives and punishments; determines how much money should be allocated to the social fund of the brigade from the earned funds; issues the results of one year's work.

The content of work outside the classroom and special boarding school is very diverse. This includes, first of all, deepening and enriching students' knowledge, teaching them to use their knowledge practically and independently, preparing students for socially useful work and, at the same time, organizing activities aimed at educating them. Then there are activities related to providing students with artistic education, developing their abilities and talents, strengthening their health, developing their physical strength, and finally organizing their cultural recreation.

Activities outside the classroom and special boarding school are organized and conducted in accordance with the goals and tasks of education and based on the initiative of students.

In addition, the age of the students, their interests and the level of preparation for this or that type of work are taken into account. It is important to take this into account, especially when determining the content and method of work. Activities outside the classroom and special boarding school should suit the strengths of students and be interesting for them.

Activities outside the classroom and special boarding school are carried out with the help of student organizations and the parents' team.

The most common form of these works are the following: circle work, public events and independent individual training of students.

The clubs that include extracurricular activities are divided into the following types;

- scientific circles;
- professional circles;
- sports clubs;
- art circles.

Due to the fact that activities outside the classroom and special boarding school are an important tool in educating students in a spiritual and moral spirit, giving them knowledge, special boarding school principals, academic directors, as well as o it is necessary to pay great attention to the teaching team, to use the support of special organizations, parents' team and special boarding school leaders in every way.

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